

THE SHADOW OF CALAMITY: EXPERIENCES OF STEM TEACHERS IN SCHOOL SERVING AS EVACUATION CENTER

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The Shadow of Calamity: Experiences of STEM Teachers in School Serving as Evacuation Center

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ABSTRACT

Baybay City Senior High School served as the evacuation center for the Barangay Kantagnos and Mailhi residents after the onslaught of Tropical Storm Agaton. This qualitative research uses the hermeneutic phenomenological design which aims to understand STEM teachers' experiences at Baybay City Senior High School in a school serving as an evacuation center. A semi-structured interview through a focus group discussion with open-ended questions was utilized. Based on the results, nine themes emerged. First is tossed into open waters which characterizes the challenges experienced by the teachers, second is a box of disarray which presents a lot of problems encountered within the school campus, third is a warm embrace on a shivering night tells us about how teachers acted on the face of the aftermath of the calamity, fourth is life's a weeping willow presents the emotional turmoil of teachers, fifth is a light in the dark tells us how teachers serve as hope and being gentle and understanding on the situation. Sixth is safe haven no more depicts the picture of how teachers feel unsafe in their own classrooms, seventh is a compass on the stormy sea tells us how teachers act as strong role models to their students, eighth is community resilience which talks about how teachers deal with the problems faced during school serving as an evacuation center, ninth theme, the antidote of a natural person tells us how a person turns to prayers showing faith in God. The study showed that teachers have negative and positive emotions toward schools serving as evacuation centers and that the role of teachers in an evacuation center is critical in ensuring the safety and welfare of the evacuees and maintaining an effective teaching-learning process. They had difficult experiences, but they were able to manage it.

Keywords: *evacuation center, teachers' feelings, teachers' experiences*

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INTRODUCTION

Cataclysms in the Philippines in the form of typhoons that result in floods and landslides are already a routine occurrence in the country. Such calamity may cast a shadow on the education system causing disruptions in classes, thus, the flow of teaching and learning are affected. Ensuring the learners' education within the shadow of calamity probably has led to public school teachers' different life experiences that may in one way or another allows them to think and act beyond the role and duty of a teacher. This study will allow us to have a closer look at teachers' lived experiences as it goes through its life amidst the shadow of calamity.

The Philippines is, and one of the many countries in Asia that is exposed to natural calamities. Provinces that are heavily populated and located near inland bodies of water are vulnerable to floods and those on the eastern side of the country are most vulnerable to typhoons. Correlational analyses on hazard vulnerability and change in school performance reveal that repeated use of school structures as evacuation centers has a negative impact on school performance (David, 2018). Furthermore, the former Department of Education Secretary Leonor M. Briones lamented and advised local government units to spare school buildings as evacuation centers during calamities so that classes will not be interrupted (Lopes, 2020).

Problems in teaching such as lack of time to finish all lessons, poor motivation and concentration of students, lack of classrooms, shortage of teaching materials, and difficulty in preparing lessons were encountered (Ardales et al., 2016, p. 29). These setbacks are probably just a few of the many experiences our teachers may have encountered. Another study conducted by Hiromi Kawasaki (2022) states that public schools have also been used as evacuation sites in other Asian countries. The involvement in both children's education and shelter operations after a disaster is stressful for teachers. Furthermore, teachers have not been educated on how to operate shelters. Such lack of training, coupled with the stressors of their job, may lead to teachers' exhaustion and burnout.

The lived experiences of teachers in the midst of the shadow of calamity have not yet been thoroughly explained. Moreno (2021) confirms that there are minimal studies addressing this topic of schooling following a natural disaster. Previous studies regarding schooling and natural disasters focused on the negative cases like the number of students who dropped out of school and the learning lost for students who did not continue attending classes (Groppo & Kraehnert, 2017; Guilbert et al., 2015; Nguyen & Minh Pham, 2018). There are few reports available that provide information about what life looks like in temporary shelters (Kawasaki et. al, 2022). Thus, this study gave us a birds-eye-view, know the in-depth lived experiences of STEM teachers in the school as evacuation centers.

Research Questions

1. What are the experiences of the STEM teachers teaching in the school serving as an evacuation center?
2. What meanings are ascribed to the experiences of teachers in a school serving as an evacuation center

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used Martin Heidegger's (1927) qualitative research approach using hermeneutic phenomenology. This design is important in this study to understand the complexity of the lived experiences of STEM teachers within the shadow of calamity. The comprehension of these lived experiences brought forth awareness and found the meanings of the phenomena. Furthermore, this research design helped in making interpretations and an in-depth understanding of the lived experiences of the research participants and in this case the STEM teachers of Baybay City Senior High School. Furthermore, through hermeneutic phenomenological design, a full understanding of what it is like to experience a specific situation such as the STEM teachers' experiences teaching in a school utilized as an evacuation center.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The research participants in this study were eight STEM teachers of Baybay City Senior High School in the school year 2021-2022. Specifically, the participants consisted of one teacher II, one teacher I, and six special science teachers.

The participants of the study were selected based on the criteria of inclusion to ensure accurate data collection. This involves identifying and selecting individuals who are knowledgeable about phenomena or interests (Cresswell & Clark, 2011). The inclusion criteria were the faculty members of the STEM Department of Baybay City Senior High School regardless of their gender, those who were already part of the teaching force when the school was converted into an evacuation center after the onslaught of tropical typhoon Agaton, and those who gave their consent to be part of the study.

The exclusion criteria include teachers who are not from the STEM department and teachers who are not part of the teaching force during evacuation.

Research Instrument

Interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audiotapes are utilized to allow for more consistent transcription (Creswell, 2009). An FGD schedule with semi-structured open-ended questions was used in this study.

During the FGD field notes and the make use of audio and video devices with permission from the research participants were utilized to capture the exact moment and to evade misinterpretations or assumptions as they foretold their lived experiences. Follow-up questions were further used to gather more important details about the study.

Data Analysis

This study used Daniela Hagele's (2022) steps in the amended interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) adapted from Smith et. al.,2009. The first step involved was familiarization with the data. In doing so, listening to the audio several times and while listening making descriptive notes of interesting and significant responses to get to know the data. By reviewing and listening well to the audio recordings several times gives more orientation on the differences as well as the common responses of the participants. Significant responses by the participants such as statements, sentences, and quotes were identified in the transcripts.

The second step was done by doing some initial notes and identifying of emergent themes from the transcripts. In this stage, organizing the data meaningfully and systematically was done as well as initial coding to reduce lots of data into small chunks of meaning.

The third step was emerging themes for each case was developed. In this case, identifying and labeling major and minor themes were done. Then these themes were grouped into clusters by labeling precise phrases or statements that described the cluster.

The fourth step was searching for connections across emergent themes for each case. So, in this case re-ordering and mapping themes and clustering related themes were done. In this way, a summary table was made that consisted of the developed themes together with their sub-theme. Quotations were made to where the relevant abstracts may be found in the transcripts.

The fifth step was done through the translation of the statements from vernacular dialects to English dialects. However, there were some statements that no longer needed translation because they were already stated in English by the participants.

The sixth step was done by making superordinate themes that developed from emergent themes and then moved to the next case. Acknowledging biases and setting aside personal feelings were taken into account. Then identifying similarities across cases was done to develop cross-case themes. After developing themes and sub-themes an interpretation of the experience was conducted.

Finally, validation of the transcription and fundamental structures of themes and sub-themes and presentation to the participants of the full results of this study to ensure that the transcription was true thus, establishing the veracity of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After a thorough analysis of the data gathered, there are Four emergent themes that reflect the experiences of the non-education graduate teachers. First, Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence, which has three sub-themes such as Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. The second theme is Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies, which has three sub-themes, namely: Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies.

This chapter presents the narrative statements from the experiences of STEM teachers in a school serving as an evacuation center. The study used interpretative phenomenological analysis of the lived experience of Baybay City Senior High School STEM teachers.

Based on the data gathered, it produced nine major themes. First is the Tossed into Open Waters has two sub-themes: Raging Sea and Emotions in Crisis. The second theme was A Box of Disarray with two sub-themes: Thick as Crude and The Songs of the Bumblebees. Third is A Warm Embrace on a Shivering Night with three sub-themes: Soothing Words, Casting a Metal of Appreciation, and, A Canvas of Gratitude. The fourth theme was Life's a Weeping Willow with two sub-themes: In Dark Despair, and Clear as a Mud. Fifth theme was A Light in the Dark with two sub-themes: Flexible as a Cat and A Spark in the Sea of Faces. Sixth theme, Safe Haven No More with the sub-themes: A Thief in the Night and A Poison Within Reach. Seventh theme, The Compass on a Stormy Sea, with two sub-themes: A Strong Role Model and A Guiding Star. Eighth theme was Community Resilience with two sub-themes: The Gentle Stream and Simplicity in a Distorted World. The ninth theme is the Antidote of a Natural Man with two sub-themes, A Simple Prayer and the Longing of the Soul.

Tossed into Open Waters

This is the first theme with two sub-themes, The Raging Sea and Emotion in Crisis. Being geographically located in the typhoon area teachers are often reminded by their school heads to secure their personal things, prepare their classrooms, and hand over the key to the security guard in the eventuality that they may be used as an evacuation center, during the aftermath of the calamity. Whenever evacuation starts, teachers together with school administration and the local government units are always at the front line to lend a helping hand to the evacuees such as aiding people in need with the responsibility to maintain safety, respect human dignity, distribute resources fairly, and make decisions transparently. This series of obligations in an evacuation center in addition to the teaching role of the teachers plus the present environmental condition she is in, it is as if she is tossed into open waters of difficulties, thus, several emotions may come into play.

The Raging Sea

This is the first sub-theme from the theme of Tossed Into Open Waters. When a school serves as an evacuation center during a disaster or crisis, it is as if teachers were in the raging sea. Teachers were not at peace with their work and their new obligations. It was a tough time and challenging for the teachers to the extent that some teachers did not know how to deal with their students, how to handle them, or how to approach them in their times of grief. Participants pointed out:

*It was actually a challenge because all the evacuees are situated in our school.
Almost all classes were affected because the buildings were used for evacuation.
It was a main challenge not just for the students but also for the teachers.*

Lines 2-7-001

I had difficulty explaining to my students. Most of my students disagree about the splitting of sections.

Lines 193-195-004

I was really challenged at first because I did not have any idea how to adjust easily to my students.

Lines 266-268-006

One of the most significant challenges during this time is the disruption to the usual routines and class schedules, to say the least. Teachers were displaced from their classrooms to pave the way for the evacuees and regular classes had to be canceled or postponed. This can be especially difficult for teachers who have already been struggling physically, emotionally, or even mentally. Furthermore, the school faced shortages of essential supplies such as food, water, and medical equipment as it tried to accommodate the large number of people seeking refuge. Sheltering, feeding, and supporting hundreds or even thousands of evacuees can be overwhelming for school administrators, teachers, and staff.

Another challenge is the emotional toil it can take on teachers working in the school-turned-evacuation center. They may be anxious, upset, or traumatized, adding to the stress and pressure of the obligations they are in. Moreover, teachers may also be personally affected by the crisis or disaster and may be struggling with their own emotions and losses. As stated by Norman, M (n.d.) teachers, staff, and administrators are not immune to similar distress. While trying to help others, they are challenged with their own lives, families, and personal loss.

Based on the results, teachers found it a tough time and challenging to embrace the new school environment after the typhoon. Everyone was affected especially the workload of the teachers. It was a tough time for them because they did not know how to approach, deal with emotionally affected students, or handle grieving students because of their loss.

Disasters are abnormal situations involving normal people, and those affected by them demonstrate an enormous range of emotional expressions. Educators who are engaged in responding to natural disasters face many challenges. Educators are sources of emotional support for students, as well as sources of academic and social education, but they have limited resources to deal with the full range of students' emotions, even in the best of situations. Educators must invariably struggle with a lack of experience and training and are confronted by the need to use strained resources in the context of a chaotic, ever-changing environment. The rules seem unclear and constantly change— this is the very nature of disasters (Norman, M. n.d.).

The results of this study show that the lack of training on how to handle or manage schools utilized as evacuation centers affects the mindset of the teachers. This is further compounded when teachers are tasked to handle face-to-face classes with their students despite the situation. It is when teachers are thrust into unfamiliar circumstances they are stressed and pressured to the extent that they can no longer handle the situation properly.

Emotion in Crises.

Stress is our physical reaction to pressure, it is a natural reaction by every living thing, such as individuals that are not able to cope with certain events same as the after-effects of natural calamities. Or when threatened that she has little or no control over the situation or is faced with unexpected new experiences, that may threaten security, safety, and the sense of self. When our emotions are in crisis, we feel worried and annoyed.

As stated by Glik (2019) in a crisis, affected people take in information, process information, and act on information differently than they would during non-crisis times. Emotion in crisis is a state of mental anguish that may be brought about by particular circumstances that can be beyond our control such as catastrophic events. This incident may give way to worry, annoyance, and sadness. When people are faced with disastrous calamities, it is not nature that is the enemy; it is themselves who are unprepared (Ronquillo. R. B., 2020). Based on her study Ronquillo further added that most of the teachers needed technical training regarding disaster preparedness.

The unpreparedness of teachers in the face of the effects of the calamity has brought different emotions to play. Some have mixed emotions, such as being happy at first that their school will be used as an evacuation center while later on when the realization sinks in they realize that they will not be able to use their classrooms. Others got feeling worried, feeling annoyed and some were stressed because of pressure. These are normal feelings, however, these strong and difficult emotions could be thwarted or minimized if teachers had been trained to understand how to handle a situation like this. Here are some experiences of teachers about emotional crises:

I uttered the words, huh! We will no longer be able to use our classrooms!

Lines 40-41-002

I really got annoyed but I just kept it to myself.

Lines 122-003

We were really worried ma'am when our section was split into two, it was really painful.

Lines 182-183-004

Though there were times that I wanted to go home to relax because of the too much stress around me.

Lines 501-503-007

Most of the time, public school teachers are always at the front liners after a disaster especially when schools are used as evacuation centers. With this, it is just appropriate that teachers and school personnel, the non-traditional first responders, must be adequately prepared and trained to avoid compassion fatigue, burnout, and further psychological injury to themselves (Domitrovich et al., 2016). The effects on teachers and school personnel when implementing trauma care without proper training have been understudied.

The 'emotion' is a specific sensation or feeling in the mind that provides directional drive to the other faculties of the mind - memory, intelligence, and physical activities - for their actions to be performed to pursue a specific goal (Das, 2017). O'Toole V. M. et al (2016) mentioned elevated rates of depression, apprehension, and fear in teachers, along with financial and personal property loss following Hurricane Katrina.

The experiences of the teachers somewhat resonated with the studies mentioned above. The degree to which teachers were affected and the kind of emotions they went through varies. But the bottom line was they were affected emotionally. Based on the responses of the participants, some of them say it was not an easy task to adjust to the sudden and rapid changes brought upon by the calamitous event that paved the way for the numerous adjustments in their teachings as well as the transferring of rooms to give way to the evacuees.

These emotions should have been checked by the school administration. Teachers have always been used as a channel to carry out services to their students but unfortunately, it is sad to note that teachers as individuals who might need post-traumatic support after a very exhaustive task in an evacuation center, are often overlooked by the school administrations

A Box of Disarray

This is the second theme which consists of two sub-themes, sub-theme 1, Thick as a Crude which includes a smelly comfort room, poops, dirty water, and trashes all around, and sub-theme number 2 The Song of the Bumblebees includes a loud environment and noisy children. Baybay City Senior High School is like a box with several elements entangled with each other. People roaming around, military and volunteer trucks come and go, the pungent odor from the scattered trash, together with animal fecal matter deposited everywhere, confusion of teachers in the transferring of rooms, the sudden change of class schedules, noises everywhere, indeed it was a total mess, a box of disarray!

As Thick as Crude

This is the second sub-theme of the second theme A Box of Disarray. Crude oil is an unrefined or thick raw product from the remains of once-lived ancient marine organisms, like algae, bacteria, and plants turned into fossils after millions of years. Unprocessed crude fuels have dark colors that have to undergo processes for them to be used.

When Baybay City Senior High School became an evacuation center, there was lots of trash, animal feces all around, smelly comfort rooms, dirty water, and human phlegms, it was as if thick as crude. This situation became an uncondusive learning environment which has caused teachers to experience stress and be unable to focus well due to the distractions from the environment while the class is in progress. This was because of the atmosphere of the school, the messy environment, and the unpreparedness of the school serving as an evacuation center.

According to the report of Mangaluz (2022), Muntinlupa City Mayor Rozzano “Ruffy” Biazon took to social media to express his anger about a local public school being left in disarray after it was used as an evacuation center during the onslaught of Severe Tropical Storm Paeng. Biazon explained that the local government typically avoids using schools as evacuation sites, as it disrupts learning and leaves facilities disorganized.

The issue of the smelly comfort room of the evacuees really affects the learning environment.

Lines 30-33-001

There was a time when I have to go to the comfort room because of personal necessity, the comfort room was so dirty that I told them to please clean the comfort room.

Lines 307-310-006

These were the same sentiments STEM teachers experienced when the school was converted to an evacuation center. Based on the results, teachers were distracted by the messy environment, and the smelly comfort rooms because the evacuees will not clean the area the way it is. There was a problem in terms of water supply, and there were some comfort rooms that were non-functional. The pets of the evacuees roamed, pooped, and urinated everywhere which contributes to the stinky smell of the school. Thus, this made the environment unconducive for learning. As I tried to assess the circumstances overpopulation and different upbringings could be the reason why evacuation centers have the same problem when it comes to cleanliness. As stated by Mosneaga (2023) overcrowding, lack of privacy and poor hygiene are just some of the commonly encountered characteristics of many evacuation centers and displacement camps that easily turn them into breeding grounds for infectious diseases. Another study by Morcillo et al. (2019) also confirms that family upbringing has an impact on the cleanliness of a person. Morcillo states that the family is the first and most important influence on the health and development of children and on the shaping of their routines, habits, attitudes, and social behaviors, including personal hygiene habits

The Song of the Bumblebees.

This is the second sub-theme of the second theme A Box of Disarray. Bumblebees (*Bombus* species) and certain solitary bees, can make a special type of “buzz” by vibrating flight muscles within the thorax. Bumblebees "*can unhinge their wings from their wing muscles and vibrate their bodies, causes the flower to explosively release pollen.*" (Ellsworth, n.d. cited in Langly, 2017). As bumblebees vibrate to release the pollen it creates a corresponding loud buzz, thus, they are known to be noisy especially when they are in a colony. Just like the overcrowded BCSHS it was so noisy like the song of the bumble bee.

When BCSHS was used as an evacuation center, the school’s usual learning environment is disrupted when used as an evacuation center. Kids roam around the alleyways, laughing, shouting, giggling, shrieking and entering classrooms without permission from the teachers. The environment was so noisy from people, vehicles and during relief operations. Too noisy that teachers have to make their voices louder to be heard enough by their students. People may have to sleep on the floor or share common spaces, leading to overcrowding and noise pollution. This can create a stressful environment for the teachers who are already too exhausted from their usual jobs and new obligations. The noise was too much that indeed it was as if they were the song of a bumblebee on a summer day. Some participants shared the different distractions they had experienced.

So far, the experiences that I had were the distractions.... Kids who were fond of running.

Lines 173-175-004

First is all about the noisy gymnasium.
Lines 402-403-008

How did they plan? People are overcrowded in every room. The gymnasium is always loud without considering the classes. So, I need to make my voice louder too.
Lines 334-337-007

Based on the result, the noise levels in a school evacuation center (gymnasium) can be particularly disturbing, especially for those individuals who are sensitive to sound. For example, the loudness of the speakers used in the gymnasium during their psychosocial activities, and noises emanating from the kids of the evacuees, who roam around and play in the alleyways during class periods. This conforms with the study of Garcia (2020) that several school children in Tuguegarao City continued studying and answering their modules amid the noise at the evacuation center following the onslaught of Typhoon Ulysses.

Noise emerging from the evacuation center is a normal occurrence, however, LGU and school administration should find ways to minimize this considering that they also have to acknowledge the ultimate role of the teachers and for them to retain their focus on teaching, and be able for them to give a positive teaching environment to their students.

A Warm Embrace on A Shivering Night

This is the third theme, a warm embrace on a shivering night tells us about the goodness of men despite the predicament. It tells us that no matter what the situation will be there is always someone who will always be there for us. When Baybay City Senior High School became an evacuation center, teachers extended their help be it a word of sympathy, or any kind to individuals affected by the calamity. This theme includes three sub-themes, cast a metal of appreciation, soothing words, and a canvas of gratitude.

Cast a Metal of Appreciation.

This is the second sub-theme of theme the Warmth Embrace on a Shivering Night. Metal casting is a process by which metals are poured into a molder where they will be formed later on depending on the type of molder, they are poured in. Just like appreciation, the way how appreciation is uttered or expressed depends on how humble a person is. Appreciation during hard times helps us survive and manage our negative emotions and at the same time improve our well-being. Being appreciative exudes positive effects on those who are affected and being of the teacher in Baybay City Senior High School in terms of being appreciative as they stated appreciative is a small way but has a lasting and meaningful impact. Below are the experiences.

At first ma'am, I appreciated it because the school or the administration, and the LGU said that the school will be used as an evacuation center. So, I was

able to tell myself it is nice for the LGU because they are cooperative in such events.

Lines 34-39-002

Teachers can see goodness even in times of difficulty. The collaboration between the local government units and the school administration was appreciated and acknowledged. The efforts of these agencies had a meaningful impact on how people discern unity in times of crisis. The good collaboration between LGU and the school administration is anchored on the Republic Act (RA) 10121 or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (PDRRM) Act. The law acknowledges that there is a need to “*adopt a disaster risk reduction and management approach that is holistic, comprehensive, integrated, and proactive in lessening the socioeconomic and environmental impacts of disasters including climate change, and promote the involvement and participation of all sectors and all stakeholders concerned, at all levels, especially the local community*” (RA 10121 of 2010, Sec. 2 (d) as cited in Itaas, et al., 2020).

Soothing Words

In the aftermath of calamity, individuals are sensitive, thus, teachers being at the forefront should know how to handle the situation. No other words can calm a soul but the soothing words of sympathy, understanding care, concern, and gentleness to someone in need. Soothing words are crucial in ensuring that everyone affected receives proper care and support. In times when schools are serving as evacuation centers, the well-being of everyone is a top priority. With limited resources, teachers must demonstrate patience, assurance, and concern when managing the needs of a large number of evacuees. They may need to coordinate with other relief agencies to ensure that everyone in the center receives the necessary resources such as food, water, and healthcare. Teachers must understand the delicate balancing act required which involves having enough supplies to meet immediate needs while conserving resources for the long haul.

Below are the experiences of teachers in Baybay City Senior High School in terms of sympathy, understanding, being gentle, extra careful, and concern as they state

So, I have to be gentle with them.

Lines 14-001

So even though the face-to-face class already started, I informed each subject teacher that I had an advisee who was the victim of Typhoon Agaton so that they would be excused from the class. They had no resources yet that time, they even asked for clothing and medicines for coughs, headaches, and colds.

Lines 65-73-003

I also asked my students if they were okay because I knew where they lived in the meantime. Unlike other main affected villages, there were overlapping relief

operations but, in their place, there was minimum to none at all. So, I handed help to them.

Lines 231-236-005

Emotions play an essential role in our daily lives, which not only influence our behaviors, attitudes, and thoughts but also influence others around us. Evidence shows that teachers' emotions greatly influence their professional development and well-being, as well as students' motivation, emotions, and multidimensional development (Li, 2022). Teachers are believed to either break or bend their learners. Having teachers who look up to the wellness of their learners through being gentle, compassionate, and patient, especially in a time when they need it most may have a lasting effect on them. The role of the teacher is not only to impart knowledge but also to help develop character-building and the best way to do it is by showing it through example.

Based on the experiences of the STEM teachers while the school was used as an evacuation center, they demonstrated soothing words, to those who may be experiencing anxiety and stress from their displacement. They were empathetic and showed understanding of the student's needs and concerns. Teachers responded to queries with a level of patience and demonstrated that they were taking their concerns seriously. A qualitative study by Jiang (2019) states that relatedness support of a teacher (involvement) represents developing positive and mutually satisfying relationships with students, such as showing affection, warmth, caring, and respect to students, and displaying interest in their activities.

A Canvas of Gratitude.

This is the third sub-theme of a theme the Warm Embrace on a Shivering Night. A canvas is an art material that is a plain, sturdy woven fabric made up of cotton or hemp yarn. Because of its quality and because it comes in all shapes and sizes, the world's best paintings are painted on canvas. Just like a canvas, a person be they rich or poor who endures hardships with a joyful heart, are individual who is filled with gratitude and gratefulness and makes the world a better place to live. These are the sharing of the participants:

I always have to remind myself to be thankful that at least I am not in the same situation as our evacuees."

Lines 503-505-007

I feel grateful and proud of myself because even if I was also a victim of tropical storm Agaton, I was able to continue my job and care for the needs of my students.

Lines 820-823-008

Grateful for the experiences because they made me strong.

Lines 913-914-006

Teachers are still grateful despite the challenges they have encountered during the nine months of school serving as an evacuation center. Grateful because the LGU was there to lend a hand. There was also consensus after addressing the different problems such as constructing additional comfort rooms and cubicles for the evacuees, cleaning the school, and instructing their children to not roam around during class hours. This made teachers appreciate and grateful to the LGU for its management.

Life's a Weeping Willow

The fourth theme was Life's a Weeping Willow which has two sub-themes, Clear as Mud consists of self-doubt, confusion, mixed emotions, and worries. And in Dark Despair which consists of depression.

A willow is an ornamental tree with beautiful pendulant branches. When rain comes, its raindrops run over its long leaves giving a picture like the tree is crying. Because of this physical characteristic, the tree is called a weeping willow, and this has always been associated with a certain point in men's lives when they are engulfed in self-doubt, confusion, mixed emotions, or even grief or sorrow.

After the calamity life felt bleak for the teachers. It was like life was turned upside-down, disoriented not knowing which direction to take to comfort their students.

In Dark Despair

Despair can be likened to the dark night of the soul. This is the point in our lives where the negative side of us imprisoned us to the point where our weakest side comes out. Despair inching its way to our soul may lead us to a moment in our lives where we are tearful, and exhausted for no apparent reason. According to Ruzickova (2022), despair can come with a range of unpleasant thoughts and emotions. We may experience fear, denial, and dismay. We may become discouraged about the future or agonize about past mistakes. Participants pointed out:

As a teacher, when my student died, I really felt as if I got depressed at that time.

Lines 275-278-006

Teachers are said to be *loco parentis*, a Latin term that means in [the] place of a parent. The frequent association of a teacher with her students develops a strong teacher-student bond. This positive teacher-student bond leads to benefits for both students and teachers, it leads to great teaching and motivated students. When this bond is broken such as the untimely death of a student, a teacher may feel at a loss. When the bond is strong, the more pain it has to do with the teacher. This explains why one of the participants in this study said that she felt depressed when she learned of what happened to her learner.

Clear as a Mud

Mud is made up of materials that make it translucent. When light strikes translucent material the light changes direction several times and is scattered as it passes through the material making it difficult to see the things on the other side of the translucent. Just like in life, when

we are not focused on something, we may develop self-doubt, confusion, and mixed emotions at certain points in our lives it shows our lack of confidence in ourselves which may show in the way we speak, we feel, and our actions. This makes us hold back in our lives which may affect our workplace, and our relationships with our loved ones, families, and, friends. When we are in a state of confusion, self-doubt, and mixed emotions our understanding is not clear making things difficult on our part to understand, thus, making things as clear as mud.

Mixed feelings refer to both happy and sad moments. This is dependent on the effect of the situation faced by the teachers. Based on the result, teachers were happy because they were proud that the school, they were working with served heartily the victims of landslides. On the other hand, they felt worried and anxious because the evacuees stayed in the school for nine months which is too long enough which makes the school uncondusive for learning. Below are the experiences of teachers on self-doubt, confusion, and mixed emotions.

I don't know how to approach the students.

Lines 11-12-001

As a teacher at the start when our school was utilized as an evacuation center, I feel worried for my students, and I went to the extent of overthinking. Having self-doubts about whether I can handle the situation, teaching in a school surrounded by negativities. I was worried about whether I can handle my students.

Lines 892-898-005

Engaging in a conversation about teachers' emotional well-being may feel superfluous to the critical conversations that are happening about the future of our schools. But the way teachers feel at and about their work has deep implications for both their own success and that of their students (Starck et al., 2022).

Frenzel et al. (2021) developed a model in which teachers' emotions affect students via three teaching behaviors: relationship building, non-verbal social messages, and instructional strategies. They also established a direct transmission effect between teachers' emotions and student outcomes (i.e., students' emotions, beliefs, motivation, discipline, and performance).

The emotional state of the teachers, when schools are converted into evacuation centers, has really to be taken care of because students look up to teachers as somebody whom they can rely on. In one of the experiences, the teacher no longer knows how to handle the students. It is worthwhile noting that the emotional state of the teacher is crucial to the academic performance of the student. So, it is just worthwhile to say that school administrators should help teachers restore sensibility and predictability.

A Light in the Dark

When people face uncertainty, obstacles, and crises in life brought about by calamitous events, or phenomenon which is beyond their control, makes them grope in the calamitous events, or

phenomenon which is beyond their control, makes them grope in the dark. However, humans as we are, no matter what obstacles we may face we live every moment to find the light that may exist in the darkness. This light may come in the form of any kind of help. There are two sub-themes on this fifth theme, Flexible as a Cat and A Spark in the Sea of Faces. When the school was utilized as an evacuation center, teachers within their means had to find ways to help in any form they could, serving as the light in the dark.

A Spark in the Sea of Faces

his is the second sub-theme. This tells us that there will always be someone who finds ways to motivate and gives a word of encouragement in a sea of faces. This someone might be a candle or a light in the dark for somebody. This tells us that as teachers they should be there to spark hope, excitement, and inspiration in the eyes of the students and bring smiles to their faces. In turn, warms the hearts of the teachers as they see their students take little steps each day toward success, giving the teachers more motivation to maximize the student's potential. Here are some shared experiences of teachers on motivation and encouragement.

*We should have a strong mindset like I need money, I need money, I need money
hahaha so that I will be motivated to continue.*

Lines 382-386-007

*I become more motivated to come to school every day and was happy to see
students learn much and come face to face with happy faces.*

Lines 713-715-001

*It encourages me to go and find ways to improve the teaching and learning
process.*

Lines 715-717-001

I was able to lift my students in times when they needed me most.

Lines 930-931-008

Based on the results there was a teacher who reasoned out that because of financial needs, a teacher was motivated to go on with the tasks in order to satisfy safety needs. The financial need of the teacher serves as the spark to go on with duties and responsibilities regardless of the condition.

As students acknowledge their teachers as someone to look up to, teachers also look up to their administrators for support in times of events when chaos and confusion take place. This can only be felt in the presence of motivation. Importantly, we also know that as much as teachers need to have technical knowledge, they also need to feel motivated to perform the challenging task of being in front of their students, who have all types of needs.

This is in line with the study of Watt and Richardson (2015), whose research on teachers' motivation has received a significant impulse focusing on three main motivation theories: expectancy-value, achievement goal, and self-determination. Importantly, other authors have

claimed that teachers' motivation cannot be explained based on the same models we hold for students, as their achievement context is different (Fives and Buehl, 2016). Regardless of these foundational arguments, it is without a doubt agreed that teachers' motivation is key to their social capital within educational systems (Han and Yin, 2016; Beusaert et al., 2021). Furthermore, the teachers' experiences prove that when motivated they can do a better job and provide the knowledge and abilities to succeed. And at the same time, the teachers are inspired by the joy and spark that they see in their student's eyes the new knowledge they have acquired.

Flexible as a Cat.

Anyone who has cats at home knows how flexible cats are. The flexibility or elasticity of these animals is based on their flexible spine and the absence of their collarbones. Though we humans do not have a flexible spine and we have collarbones, we are flexible in terms of reaching out to others. We also adapt and accept things as it is and find ways how to overcome such obstacles.

Teachers who are working at such centers must have flexibility and adaptability to meet the changing needs of the people they are serving. Teachers can be flexible during school serving as evacuation centers. Responding to individual needs: Teachers must be able to identify the needs of each individual and respond to them accordingly. Some people may require medical assistance, mental health counseling, or financial support. Teachers must be willing to adjust their schedules and roles to address these needs.

Acceptance in terms of schools serving as evacuation centers depend on various factors, including location, capacity, coordination, impact on education, and resource allocation. Schools can play a critical role in providing emergency shelter, but there is a need for careful consideration and planning to ensure they are well-equipped to offer these services, without negatively impacting education and students' well-being. The prospect of a school serving as an evacuation center may pose some challenges for teachers, acceptance of the situation can be rooted in a sense of duty, collaboration, resilience, and understanding of the greater good. Here are some shared experiences of teachers on flexibility.

So, I have to be gentle with them and I have to adjust to all their needs. That's it.. as a teacher, or a facilitator I need to guide them. The turning point at that time ma'am, I have to accept that it was already done.

Lines 14-18-001

One thing we have to adjust is the unexpected things that will happen.

Lines 320-321-006

I did my best to find ways to be able to help my students cope with the situation. I gave them additional reading materials and did some one-on-one tutorials for those who have difficulty understanding my topic because at least through that they will not have the difficulty once we go to the next lessons. Just making sure that the foundation of the topic is strong.

Lines 522-530-001

That's why I told my advisory class to accept and welcome the students from Einstein for the meantime because of the Kantagnos evacuees, our room is not enough to cater all the students for face-to-face classes. We deal the challenges through acceptance. Accepting the situation. It was already happened, we cannot control it, it was a natural calamity.

Lines 466-474 -008

Teachers may accept the fact that the school is being used as an evacuation center because they know that it is for the greater good. Acceptance is important because Makwana (2019) pointed out that evacuees are more vulnerable to stress, anxiety, and other different maladaptive reactions after the disaster. In times of natural disasters or emergencies, it is essential to provide shelter and support to those affected, and schools can play a crucial role in this. Teachers may feel a sense of duty and responsibility towards the community and view the use of the school as an evacuation center to contribute to the welfare of those in need. It is an opportunity to make a positive impact and help those impacted by the disaster. Some teachers may have been trained to handle emergency situations and may view the use of the school as an evacuation center as an opportunity to put their training into practice. For them, it may be a chance to demonstrate their skills and readiness to deal with emergencies.

The study revealed that lots of teachers have demonstrated adaptability, acceptance, and flexibility to their students this tells us that the teachers are not bound to only teach and impart knowledge to their students but they are also flexible to their students' needs. Being flexible helps the teacher to easily accept the situation and move forward to continue a positive engagement with their students. The flexibility that teachers demonstrate might be the reason why no confrontation took place between the teachers, students, and the evacuees.

Safe Haven No More

This is the sixth theme with two sub-themes, A Thief in the Night and A Poison Within Reach. Safe haven refers to a place or situation where one can feel secure, protected, and at ease. Teachers most of the time put some of their valuables that are needed in their day-to-day function as teachers in their classroom. Teachers also feel secure that no cigarettes are sold on the school campus. However, in reality, safe havens sometimes become unsafe when a school is converted to an evacuation center that caters to lots of people of different backgrounds, motives, and attitudes.

A Thief in the Night

This is the sub-theme of the sixth theme Safe Haven No More. Teachers are so trusting that sometimes they forget that the once-secure place of work is still the same, they forget that once a school is converted to an evacuation center there are already lots of people of divergent backgrounds living in it. Furthermore, in an evacuation center, there is no foolproof security when it comes to the flow of people coming in and out of the school. For a teacher, it is sad to know when a classroom not intended for evacuees but for instructional purposes, is being forcefully opened by a thief in the night.

The last experience that I can share is during that time safety is at risk. My room was robbed and there were other similar incidents too. That's why I decided to double lock my room so that they cannot destroy it easily.

Lines 450-454-008

This statement is the same as Ardales (2016) that school furniture, appliances, and equipment were either damaged or completely destroyed. Teaching materials, school records, reports, and documents were also ruined. Light bulbs, doorknobs, and other room fixtures were destroyed and many were stolen. Another study by Arcayera, R.A. A. (n.d.) mentioned that Incidents of looting became widespread in schools. Blotter report showed that there were items missing from teachers like three solane tanks from Bread and Pastry and Cookery laboratories, three Epson printers, sets of computer laboratory curtains, a speaker, lapel, microphones, school items, waste dispenser, garbage bins, and many school items. This common incident was affirmative and most learning resources like modules were scattered and used as “*trapos or higdaan*” (rags or mats) of some evacuees.

This is the usual occurrence in some evacuation centers. When a school is used as an evacuation shelter, the fear that every teacher has is the safety of their property. This explains why one teacher participant in this study used a double lock in a classroom to discourage further robbery from taking place again. It is sad to note that teachers sacrifice their classrooms to give shelter to those in need. Most teachers even go to the extent of tidying their rooms to welcome the evacuees. However, things like this do exist.

A Poison Within Reach

According to the American Lung Association (2023), a single cigarette approximately contains 600 ingredients and when burned, its smoke contains 7,000 chemicals and 69 of these chemicals are carcinogenic. Many of these chemicals also are found in consumer products, but these products have warning labels – such as rat poison packaging. While the public is warned about the danger of the poisons in these products, there is no such warning about the toxins in tobacco smoke. In this study, this refers to how some evacuees sold cigarettes to some learners which is a big no to a school campus. This experience was reflected below as the participant said:

But I feel sad that some evacuees are not very cooperative and that some of them even went to the extent of selling cigarettes to the students.

Lines 924-927-007

As per the Department of Education Order No. 48, s. 2016 or the Policy and Guidelines on Comprehensive Tobacco Control, DepEd shall undertake awareness activities to warn against smoking and counter efforts of the tobacco industry to downplay or deny the harmful nature of tobacco products (DepEd. 2016). As mentioned by then Department of Education Secretary Briones in a forum with other government agencies (Malipot, 2022). “We have long integrated key tobacco control concepts in our curriculum, while we have also regularly conducted and participated in various co-curricular activities to increase awareness among our learners about the ill-effects of tobacco use,” The statement made by Secretary Briones further establishes a firm reminder that smoking is prohibited in school.

The Department of Education did its best to curtail cigarette smoking among the youth. As stated by Dr. Briones, “Since 2016, the DepEd has institutionalized comprehensive tobacco control policy that prohibits smoking near schools and among learners” (DepEd. 2022). This mandate gave teachers from public schools the assurance that smoking is prohibited within the school grounds. However, when Baybay City Senior High School became an evacuation center, cigarettes were within reach by the learners. This circumstance which was the selling of cigarettes to the learners by the evacuees somewhat caused the school to be in a position where it was no longer a safe haven. This event concerned and saddened a teacher. This was one of the issues that took concern between the City Social Welfare and Development and the school administration.

A Compass on A Stormy Sea

This is the seventh theme with two sub-themes, A Strong Role Model and a Guiding Star. Like a compass that guides the correct direction, teachers provide or navigate their students in the appropriate direction that may guide them in their journey for a good future. In times of chaos, and confusion such as when schools are serving as evacuation centers and at the same time as edifices for educational instruction, teachers are there serving as a compass for their students.

Strong Role Model

This is the first sub-theme of the theme Compass on a Stormy Sea. Teachers play a critical role in the lives of students during natural disasters or emergencies when schools are transformed into evacuation centers. These teachers act as strong role models for students who require assistance, guidance, and support in times of crisis. Teachers need to be prepared and equipped with the necessary communication and leadership skills to ensure the safety and well-being of students. This study refers to the actions of teachers as strong role models. From their experiences, they pointed out that:

So, I have to...as a teacher, I have to be the strong model...strong..strong role model for the students.

Lines 18-21-001

Correct! I agree with the mindset and strong emotions. You should not let the students feel that you are affected because we are role models.

Lines 674-677-006

As a teacher, we will use our masks. It's just like that. We need to show compassion to the students at the same time one emotion at a time. Do not let the students sense your weakness.

Lines 678-682-007

There are theories and principles followed by people around the world to demonstrate leadership. However, very few become role models. When it's a competitive situation, we need

leaders to navigate the way, guide us, coach us, and help us to perform better to achieve. But in tough times and in crisis, people in general may be clueless, fearful, lack confidence, and may lose in the process. That is the time when we need more leaders who can lead by example—inspire, influence, challenge, and become Role Models in the process (Das 2020).

A role model is a person who inspires and encourages us to strive for greatness, live to our fullest potential, and see the best in ourselves. A role model is someone we admire and someone we aspire to be like. We learn through them, through their commitment to excellence, and through their ability to make us realize our own personal growth. We look to them for advice and guidance. Much of what students learn from their greatest teachers is not detailed on a syllabus.

Teachers who help us grow as people are responsible for imparting some of life's most important lessons. During their initial school years, students encounter, perhaps for the first time, other children of the same age and begin to form some of their first friendships. As a teacher, you will show your students how to become independent and form their relationships, you will carefully guide them and intervene when necessary. School is as much a place of social learning as academic learning, and this is true, not only in our early years of education but through college. Armed with a supportive and well-educated administration, there is no limit to the influence a teacher can have on one, or many, students' lives. Though a teacher's influence on the social sphere of school lessens as students mature, those early lessons still affect how they will interact with others in the future.

Teachers are fountains of experience. They have already been where their students are going, undergone what they will go through, and are in a position to pass along lessons, not only regarding the subject matter but also lessons on life (Teachers are role models. 2023). Teachers serve as role models by upholding values such as patience, kindness, and empathy. Teachers demonstrate a positive attitude towards students, their families, and community members who have been affected by the crisis. They exhibit patience with the children and reassure them of their safety and well-being. Teachers also demonstrate kindness by accommodating the individual needs of students and ensuring they are comfortable at the evacuation center. Lastly, teachers are responsible for organizing activities and routines that engage and educate students. They provide constructive activities that allow students to express themselves positively, learn new skills, and restore normalcy. Teachers offer guidance on healthy habits, such as keeping clean, staying healthy, and relaxing the mind during challenging times.

Based on the result, teachers act as a source of comfort for students during a traumatic experience. They provide students with a safe environment, reassurance, and an opportunity to connect with others who are also going through a similar situation. Teachers calm students' anxiety by offering assurance, encouragement, and emotional support throughout the crisis. This conforms Sharma (2016) statement that an empathetic attitude inside the class brings out the humane side of not only the teacher but is also instrumental in inculcating the same in the students. It motivates them to discuss issues with their teachers and try to find solutions to the problems they face. Teachers' actions of showing empathy and compassion are a form of humane education as stated by Cieslak (2019) that encourages students to practice empathy by putting themselves in another's shoes and thus encourages compassion which is the desire to take action to alleviate the suffering of others. Empathy and compassion are essential components of education.

Teachers are role models and that explains why we have the Filipino expression, “*Teacher ka pa naman.*” (You are a teacher) which is sarcasm towards a teacher. True role models are those who possess the qualities that we would like to have, and those who have affected us in a way that makes us want to be better people. They help us to advocate for ourselves and take a leadership position on the issues that we believe in. Role models show young people how to live with integrity, optimism, hope, determination, and compassion. They play an essential part in a child’s positive development (Teachers as role Models, 2021).

In the eyes of the students, teachers are role models that can influence their behavior, character, attitudes, and values. Being a strong role model to students means that even in times of struggle teachers cannot falter and show weakness when their students need them the most. They are the guiding light of the students as they venture through the confusing episodes in their lives.

A Guiding Star.

Based on the teachers’ experiences teachers act as someone whom students can look up to. They were there to guide the students in their lessons had a one-on-one tutorial, took into consideration the pacing of the students and some went to the extent of visiting them in their homes. Below are the experiences they mentioned.

I did my best to find ways to be able to help my students cope with the situation. I gave them additional reading materials and did some one-on-one tutorials for those who have difficulty understanding my topic because at least through that they will not have the difficulty once we go to the next lessons. Just making sure that the foundation of the topic is strong.

Lines 522-530-001

The situation is inevitable. I have to visit all my students who were victims of the Barangay Kantagnos landslide not only to check their progress academically but also to check on their well-being. I always see to it that they are ok emotionally and be with them. I did that always because I am concerned about their mental health and I know that what had happened to them was not an ordinary case.

Lines, 559-567-002

I also took into consideration the pacing of my students especially those who were victims of the Barangay Kantagnos landslide. I see to it that they fully understand the topic before I move to the next topic so that they will not have difficulty grasping whatever topic may be discussed.

Lines 568-573-002

Based on this result, teachers are like the northern star they shine bright in the dark night guiding their students through this catastrophe. This is further established by the experiences in which it was never stated to them that they needed to comfort their students and provide home visits. However, the teachers went out of their way to check on their student's mental and

physical well-being. These are the unstated responsibilities that a teacher fulfills for their students acting as their guiding light.

Without a teacher, an individual stands nowhere! Teachers are our guiding light who help us so that we can touch the limits of the sky. Although no one can replace a parent's affection towards their child yet teachers perceive each child objectively in a formal environment, free from the wings of extreme parenting emotions, which helps in providing an unbiased assessment of a child's strengths and weaknesses that further helps in handling their problems in a more professional yet careful and loving manner (Pathak, 2021)

Community Resilience

This is the eighth theme with two sub-themes The Gentle Streams and Simplicity in a Distorted World. Resilience is critical at all three levels. As a building block of school preparedness towards calamity being able to withstand the impacts of adverse events both mentally and physically as an individual makes a person more valuable to the response and recovery operations of the event. This in turn allows teachers, to better serve the students, school, and community. Communities may be defined not only based on geographic location, but also by how individuals self-organize and identify themselves with organizations such as local government units, civic groups, neighborhood associations, and parent-teacher associations among others. Within a specific community, resilient individuals have a larger impact on others.

The Gentle Streams

This is the first sub-theme of the eighth theme Community Resilience. Like a a stone in the river no matter how sharp its edges are, with the continuous flow of the water its sharp edges will be smoothed as the gentle stream continuously flows over the rock through time. This is like collaboration, the persistently positive sharing of ideas creates a culture that is conducive for teachers to reach out to department heads, and school administration in a collaborative manner.

My experience as a teacher is the success of the learners was measured based on the minimization of problems encountered by the teachers as well as students contributed by the environment. They were comforted by the action of the school administration and local government units who found ways to mitigate conflicts and situations affecting school learning conditions. The improvement of environmental conditions helps students and teachers alike to focus on the learning tasks delivered efficiently which enhances the learning absorption of the student. Ummm...it is because.. based on my observation as a teacher the performance of the learners improved and the efficient and effective delivery of lessons was carried out to maximum level even with the presence of day-to-day challenges of life.

Lines 694-712-001

As a teacher, I realized that the collaboration between the teachers, school administration, and the LGU paved the way for how the teachers were able to manage the new learning environment.

Lines 789-793-005

The ability of teachers to promote character-building in terms of patience understanding cooperation, consideration, and resilience coped with the day-to-day challenges in the school.

Lines 775-779-004

Based on the result, teachers coordinate with the authorities and other agencies. The teachers ensured coordination with the authorities responsible for managing the evacuation center. Teachers worked in tandem with other agencies to provide the necessary supplies and resources to the evacuees at the same time maintaining the momentum of productive teaching and learning.

Cooperation among parents, teachers, and students is considered necessary to ensure the safety of the schools and allow children to receive regular instruction. However, nothing has been written about the environment needed to enable teachers to devote their efforts to continuing education at schools that serve as evacuation centers (Kawasaki, H. 2021).

Collaborative networks of schools and communities can also actively receive the support needed after disasters. It has been found that schools contribute to collaborative community networks while providing mutual benefits to other interested parties in the networks (Oktari, R.S. 2018). Both rural and urban schools have the same opportunities to build partnerships with school boards, educational authorities, families, and communities. Collaboration is possible regardless of the circumstances of the community (Sakurai, A. 2018). Building collaborative relationships with educational institutions, school boards, parents, families, regional communities, and other stakeholders presents an important opportunity to increase the ability of a community to recover from a disaster. The experience of the teacher correlates with the above study that collaboration with teachers, school administrators, LGU, and evacuees results in a manageable learning environment, and as mentioned by Russel (n.d.) cooperation among parents, teachers, and students is considered necessary to ensure the safety of the schools.

Simplicity in a Distorted World

This is the second sub-theme of the eighth theme Community Resilience. Wherever, whatever the situation may be, be it in a peaceful setting or a community within the shadow of calamity good communication only needs a simple recipe or a good blueprint: Simplicity is language and an expression that makes complex ideas and thoughts clear making way for a peaceful environment.

Communication is important to have stable results in the community. In addressing different challenges, proper communication is important so that it will be solved easily. This study showed how teachers communicated with their students and let them understand the situation

and why there are adjustments in terms of the usage of the classroom. Teachers also communicated to the students who were victims of the Agaton to see the brighter side of life. In other words, there were words of wisdom to encourage students to continue their journey amidst calamity. Based on the result, the problems were addressed because of proper communication. Teachers also communicated with the evacuee's kids and their elders to have a peaceful teaching and learning environment.

At the same time, innovating something to address the challenge. I talked the kids to refrain from playing in the alleyways when classes were going on. But there were others who doesn't know how to listen so I did was talk to the older people of Barangay Kantagnos and reported the distraction, hoping in some way they might be able to help us. A few days after I reported the incidents, seldom of the kids roamed around the alleyways to play.

Lines 474-484-008

Just making sure that the foundation of the topic is strong. I... reported the situation to our heads and I know that they did their part by letting the concerned people from the local government unit know about our situation from the grounds. So far there was an action that took place because evacuees started to clean their areas, the kids already stopped playing around the alleyways, and students started to focus on our topics because of that it was as if we were back to our normal settings.

Lines 529-539-001

Meetings with other sectors of the community were made to solve issues affecting the operation of the evacuation centers.

Lines 802-805-005

As mentioned by Satyendra (2020) communication is from a Latin word 'communis', which means common or shared understanding. Communication is hence a purposeful effect to establish commonness between a source and a receiver. Whatever is being shared can be associated with knowledge, experience, thought, ideas, suggestions, opinions, and feelings etc. In its simplest form, communication is the transmission of a message from a source to a receiver, or the process of creating shared meaning. Communication has crucial impacts on the working of the employees in the organization. The organizational communication is a channel for the flow of information, resources, and even policies. It is also be broadly defined as communication with one another in the context of an organization. This type of communication, in turn, includes activities of sending and receiving messages through various layers of authority, using various message systems, and discussing various topics of interest to the group. For instance, in an emergency, what needs to be done should be expressed in clear and simple language to evacuees. Instructions should be precise and repeatedly presented. Teachers need to be able to use clear and easy-to-understand words for adults, give accurate instructions, and present them repeatedly as needed.

The purpose of communication is to achieve coordinated action, express feelings and emotions, share information regarding organizational goals, task directions, results of efforts, and

decision-making, achieve effective control, encourage employees' participation in decision-making, and create a good public image and reputation for the organization.

Improving teachers' communication skills to provide education and guidance to residents concerning community needs and specific approaches to disaster management are recommended (Kawasaki, H. 2020). Teachers need to communicate with students' parents, so they gain the skill of communication with parents regarding cooperation. However, teachers are not used to communicating with evacuees who are not parents of their students. In an emergency, communication with the evacuees increases. So, teachers need to acknowledge the need to practice speaking with the evacuees. Based on the result, the issues that crop up such as the noise of the kids, and the untidiness in the evacuation center were addressed because of proper communication. Results show that the sincere communication of teachers with department heads, the evacuees, and the kids improved the situation of the school. This implies that with the proper use of communication, everything can be achieved smoothly, and taught us a lesson that through proper communication something positive will be possible.

The Antidote of the Human Being

This is the ninth theme with two sub-themes, A Simple Prayer and The Longing of the Soul. Religiousness is expressed by religious practices, the fulfilling of duties stemming from convictions. Prayer is one of these activities. The word "prayer" has many meanings, as we call "prayer" also the thanksgiving, praising the glory of God, or joy of the beauty of creation. The person who expresses gratitude to God, also recognises his dependence and asks God to let him continue enjoying his goodwill.

According to the research of Bentzen (2019) finds that people become more religious when hit by natural disasters. They are more likely to rank themselves as a religious person, find comfort in God, and to state that God is important in their lives. This increase in average religiosity occurs on all continents, for people belonging to all major religions, income groups, and from all educational backgrounds.

A qualitative study by Swalachowski (2021) states that the literature on connection between religiousness and experience of fears reveals two completely different causes: (a) *fear that motivates religious faith*, and (b) *faith that alleviates the fear*. The first is associated with the feeling of helplessness in the face of imminent annihilation. Hence the answer is "effort", "imagination", "illusion" or "wish" that encourage to follow the concept of immortality, be it literal or symbolic. The foundations of this term are usually the affirmation of the existence of supernatural creatures, the practicing of certain rituals and regulating of attitudes by moral codes. This shows that all this religious experience alleviates the anxiety triggered by the awareness of one's own finiteness. Therefore, religious persons could enjoy a lower level of fear thanks to their rituals, norms, social relationships and system convictions (Meza 2020). Exactly prayer is an element of practice, the basic factor of man's religious life (Woroniecki 2018).

A person, by nature, is a sinner, it is inherent as a mortal being that regardless of how a person tries to be pious, still, everyone is vulnerable to sin. Prayer is an antidote from the negativities in life.

A Simple Prayer

Being thankful to God is already a prayer. As stated by Hovater (2023) word of thank you to God is considered a simple prayer, but the most essential prayer.

I am grateful and thankful to God that I was able to impart to my students that life has its own twist and turns and we have to choose what is best not just for us but for everybody.

Lines 876-879-002

Thus, at the start of my class, I asked my students to close their eyes and follow what I say, "I offer you peace. I offer you love. I offer you friendship. I hear your needs, I am not blind to your sufferings, I feel your feelings and for that let us work hand-in-hand for unity, understanding, patience, and peace." This has allowed me to awaken the hearts of my learners and they started to see the reality of life and accept eventualities that were beyond our control."

Lines 586-596-005

Based on the statement of the teachers, they believe Divine intervention would comfort them, especially in desperate times. Prayers give hope and light to those who are in grief. Like any other calamities, Filipinos portrayed a strong religious faith that remained steadfast during these emergencies. While the pandemic brought individuals and families in isolation, it did not stop the Filipino Catholic faithful from expressing their faith but made it stronger, with a firm conviction that the grace of God could protect them from the pandemic (Cañete, 2021).

Studies show that people tend to intensify their prayer activities having exhausted other ways to cope or when the situation looks desperate, and when these factors are taken into account, the apparently negative relation between prayer and psychological health disappears. According to the theory on religious coping (Bentzen, 2019) people mainly use religion to cope with large, negative, and unpredictable events. Using religion for coping is part of what is termed emotion-focused coping, in which people aim to reduce the emotional distress arising from a situation. When people face perceived negative, but *predictable* events, such as an approaching exam or a job interview, they are more likely to engage in problem-focused coping, where they aim to tackle directly the problem that is causing the stress. It has also been revealed that people tend to engage more strongly in prayer when problems are acute, chronic or when other ways to cope fail (Sinding Bentzen 2019; Bentzen 2020; Ellison et al. 2001 as cited in Swalachowski 2021).

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

After a thorough analysis of the data gathered, there are Four emergent themes that reflect the experiences of the non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation.

First, Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence, which has three sub-themes such as Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. The second theme is Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies, which has three sub-themes, namely: Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, Prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies. The third theme is Collaborative Professional Enhancement, which has three sub-themes which are Promoting Peer Collaboration, Optimizing Observer Interaction, and Resourceful Teaching Practices. The fourth theme is Navigating Challenges in Classroom Observation, which has four sub-themes, these are: Performance Stress and Burnout, Knowledge and Resource Gaps, Tackling Logistical Hurdles, and Uncharted Feedback.

Conclusion

Results gathered from the experiences of non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation concluded that these experiences exerted a profound and comprehensive influence on the participants' personal, professional, and emotional well-being as a teacher both positively and negatively. It is concluded that there is a need to fill the gap in knowledge of different pedagogies specific to the learning objectives is extremely important to capacitate non-education graduate teachers to become more effective educators. Likewise, participants had experienced difficulty in the crafting of the Lesson Plan which is equally important to ensure coherent and well-structured delivery of the lesson. It was also revealed that there are no enough learning materials in the senior high school which is more content-wise to be utilized by most of the teachers. Non-education graduate teachers also need to resolve their personal struggles such as anxiety, self-doubt, and uneasiness towards the observation. Lastly, participants had experienced the absence of a post-observation conference which should be religiously conducted to all teachers who have undergone classroom observation not just to evaluate themselves but also to glean valuable insights for ongoing improvement, Given the result of this study, it is concluded further that there is a need to capacitate non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation with respect to the challenges they have encountered.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn based on the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. Capacitate teachers on different teaching pedagogies aligned to their subject area through seminars, In-Service Education and Training (INSET), and School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions.
2. Integrate lesson planning sessions as part of the orientation for the newly hired and non-education graduate teachers at the start of the school year.
3. Innovate locally-made and quality-assured learning materials to compensate for the lack of learning resources in senior high school.
4. Engage teachers in a series of Psychosocial activities throughout the year such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques, and emotional regulation workshops which can help them manage their personal struggles related to classroom observation.

5. Encourage school heads, department heads, and master teachers who act as observers to religiously conduct post-observation conferences right after the observation schedule.
6. Conduct further study in the field of non-education graduate teachers.

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